

Visiting the Margins.

INnovative CULTural ToUrisM in European peripheries

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1 Summary

This report contains three parts: In the first part, it discusses stakeholder analysis and mapping as applied to tourist destinations and more specifically, to the INCULTUM network of Pilots. Secondly, a stakeholder mapping exercise is applied to all the ten Pilots based on data gathered by the group of analysts of CBS, WP7 lead, and by SDU as leader of WP3. Lastly, the preliminary conclusions sum up the work done and focus on the challenges with a view to the coming tasks to be completed, especially those related to impact, evaluation, and exploitation (T7.2 and T7.3). The content of this report has therefore required the collaboration of the SDU as lead of WP3 as well as all the pilots.

The 10 pilots are spread over very varied territories and with different characteristics and evolution. Understanding the operation of each pilot, as well as the identification of each local stakeholder, and to afterwards include them all in a stakeholder analysis is a difficult task, not least due to the different stages of development that the pilots find themselves in. We shall return to these difficulties in the analysis and especially in chapter 6.

2 Introduction

The Grant Agreement (GA) states that “innovative cultural tourism can be used as a driver for innovation and cooperation, promoting sustainable economic development in local communities, their participation and their specific contexts” (GA, Part B, p. 8). INCULTUM is thus founded upon the central idea that an untapped potential exists in sustainable cultural tourism, which is completely in line with the EU policies on the subject that aim to promote cultural tourism balancing the need for growth and development with “preservation of artefacts, historical sites, and local traditions”¹.

For the purposes of this project, INCULTUM follows the definition of cultural tourism made by the UNWTO as “a type of tourism activity in which the visitor’s essential motivation is to learn, discover, experience and consume the tangible and intangible cultural attractions/products in a tourism destination. These attractions/products relate to a set of distinctive material, intellectual, spiritual and emotional features of a society that encompasses arts and architecture, historical and cultural heritage, culinary heritage, literature, music, creative industries and the living cultures with their lifestyles, value systems, beliefs and traditions”².

The UNWTO’s definition thus includes both the local residents and the tourists. In fact, in cultural tourism, at least two collectives (locals and visitors) each with their own collective identity, meet and interact. It is a distinct goal of INCULTUM that neither of these social identities suffers unwanted changes, and the project aims to make sure that the social identities involved will be only positively affected, increasing the local’s pride in local heritage, forms of production, natural scenery, etc., on the one hand, and fomenting the visitors’ curiosity and knowledge about the destination in all its aspects, on the other. In our view, this is the only way to counter the negative, and often denaturalising, effects of touristification specifically and of tourism in general. The risk is perhaps even larger in areas suffering from unemployment, underdevelopment, and depopulation, since locals may be more tempted in such areas to stop doing what they used to do because they can earn more by catering for tourists.

2.1 Role of the deliverable in the Work package and in the project

By implementing cultural tourism innovations that are created in the pilots, the main purpose of WP7 is to ensure as much positive social, cultural, environmental, and economic impact as possible on local communities by implementing cultural tourism innovations that are created within the pilots. But the point is that the demand side – the market for cultural tourism – and the supply side – local economic and social development – depend on each other. The synergies that INCULTUM aims for will happen if focus is kept both on the local level as well as on the cultural tourists – both actual and prospective – whose visit is the whole point of the project. Cultural tourism, which is the main means to achieve the goals of INCULTUM, simply will not happen without tourists visiting the pilot areas.

The principal level of action within INCULTUM is thus the local/regional level related to the ten Pilots and the activities undertaken there. But in a second instance, the goal of the project is to ensure cross-fertilisation between the pilots and beyond, which means that - whenever possible -

¹ European Commission (2021): “Cultural tourism.” Accessed 02/12/2021 from https://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/tourism/offer/cultural_da.

² UNWTO (2017): *Tourism and Culture*. Accessed 22/11/2021 from <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-and-culture>.

the other nine pilots will serve as the first testing ground of the solutions that any of the pilots implement. This possibility of cross-fertilisation will of course be based strictly on a relevance criterion, due to the fact that not all pilots serve as testing ground for all the pilot solutions, but all innovations should be relevant to various other pilots. Thirdly, the pilot solutions are to be spread among the wider network of interested stakeholders, and it is the responsibility of WP7 to monitor and advance these exploitation activities related to the INCULTUM pilot solutions, their marketability and upscaling.

However, the ten pilots are also very different both in terms of content and focus as well as in terms of level of development. They find themselves at very different levels of development; some are already well-established, while others are only now coming into being. In the latter case, the network of stakeholders is by no means fully established yet. The huge differences between the pilots and the complexity of the whole project makes it imperative to reflect on how to ensure a minimum alignment and the best cross-fertilisation between pilots. The stakeholder mapping precisely serves this aim and is fundamental to begin to achieve these aims and to perform any later analysis related to impact and exploitation. The stakeholders will be mapped in both the present situation as well as a prospective future and the map is as detailed as possible at this stage, highlighting the challenges in this regard. It covers the period of the first six months of the project and is supposed to feed the preparations for the Impact, Evaluation, and Exploitation plan (D7.2) due 12 months from now (month 18). This next deliverable will cover the actions undertaken from month 7 to 18 and lay the foundations for the final version of that deliverable (D7.3) due in month 34.

2.2. Aims and scope

The present stakeholder analysis will include both descriptive, instrumental, and normative elements (see e.g. [Parmar, Freeman, & Harrison, 2010](#) for a critical overview), with the descriptive aspect being foregrounded in the present initial phase. Thus, to gain a firmer basis for addressing normative issues (what should be done?) and instrumental issues (how can it be done?) in follow-up work, a detailed, realistic, and operational picture is needed of the key actors and of the specific constellations of interests, goals, opportunities, and barriers that characterize each pilot. This report lays down the cornerstone for and presents the results gained so far in that work while at the same time being intended as a living document that will be updated and extended during the first two thirds of the project (until and including Month 23).

2.3 Key sources

Main empirical input for first version of stakeholder map:

- 1 Semi-structured qualitative interviews conducted with representatives of the pilots. Each individual pilot was investigated through interviews between a CBS research assistant and (a) team member(s) from the pilot in question's responsible partner. These interviews were an important method in the collection of data, as they allowed for an in-depth overview of where the pilots stand within their progression, what works, what the problems are, where knowledge is lacking, and so forth.
- 2 Qualitative and quantitative data extracted from the existing project documentation, findings made by other WPs (in particular the responses to the pilot questionnaire conducted by SDU as part of WP3), reports, stakeholder homepages, online and printed media. Through these various forms of documentation, survey analyses, statistics and other (hard) facts were able to be extracted.

- 3 Official webpages supplied further elaboration of acquired information and definitions of relevant concepts.

3 Overview of central stakeholder categories and features across Pilots

This section presents an overarching framework that offers an operational conceptual basis for the detailed analyses of stakeholder relations in the present report and, no less importantly, in further extensions and diversifications of the analyses as INCULTUM progresses. Selected examples will furthermore be given of how the suggested categories manifest themselves differently in different pilots, setting the scene for the more detailed analysis of the individual pilots following in sections 4 and 5. This includes variations in the understanding of cultural tourism as an overall concept.

3.1 Major stakeholder categories

The number and delimitation of stakeholder categories addressed in analyses of tourism stakeholder relations vary profoundly depending on the intended depth and specific purpose(s) of the analyses (e.g. [Roxas, Rivera, & Gutierrez, 2020](#); [Alonso & Nyanjom, 2017](#); [Cowley & Gillmore, 2008](#)) This is also true of the styles of visualisations used (see [Cenek & Částek, 2016](#), for an overview). Below we identify and name such stakeholder categories that must necessarily be taken into account for addressing the full array of issues inherent in the INCULTUM agenda. The categories may however be both further diversified and collapsed into more inclusive categories to meet particular descriptive and analytical needs as the work progresses.

Overview of main types of stakeholders (further diversified in visual maps):

- Tourists
- Authorities and policy makers
- Local action groups
- Local farmers, food producers, craftsmen, artists
- Infrastructure providers
- Accommodation providers
- Tourism operators
- Shopping and leisure facilities
- Workforce
- Investors
- Academia
- Educational sector
- IT application developers

Figure 1 provides an overview of these categories in visual form.

Figure 1. Overview of key stakeholder categories.

Figure 2 (below) further diversifies the roles played by these different categories of stakeholders in meeting the overarching goal of transforming the target territories of the 10 Pilots into successful cultural tourism destinations. The most crucial stakeholder groups in that regard are, on the one hand, the tourist who currently visit and, in particular, who might in the future consider visiting the target territories. And, on the other hand, the local communities who will host them and act as primary drivers of local tourism on the spot. This is illustrated by the left-hand and the right-hand part of the figure, respectively. The tourist may be further divided into segments by a number of generic (taxonomic) criteria as indicated in Figure 2 and taken a step further in Figure 3 below. The local communities, in turn, may be further analysed in terms of their constitutive elements and actors (i.e., applying a part-whole perspective), each contributing in different but mutually dependent ways to the successful development of cultural tourism. The same is true for actors located outside the target territories on which the implementation of the set goals also ultimately depends, as indicated by the green circle. This includes the INCULTUM consortium as a whole.

Figure 2. Key contributors to the promotion of cultural tourism in the target territories.

Figure 3 adds a few more dimensions to the basic picture just outlined by indicating that some key stakeholder categories can manifest themselves geographically both within and outside the target territories while others are intrinsically local. For instance, local craftsmen, food producers and other actors potentially attracting tourism must necessarily be found within the target territory. By contrast, other stakeholders may be more dispersed geographically, such as interested investors who may be either local, national or foreign, while media potentially supporting a positive coverage of the territories (or generating negative coverage) may also be found locally, nationally and globally. The latter may indeed include the tourist themselves; say, enthusiastic bloggers spreading information by electronic word-of-mouth. The left-hand part of the figure furthermore integrates a number of the more specific dimensions along which relevant tourist segments may be crystallised, combining partitive relations (here: part-whole relations between sub-groups) and generic relations (interests, budgets, etc.) applicable within and across groups (see e.g. [Suonuuti, 2001](#) and [ISO 704:2009](#) on the subdivision principles applied).

Figure 3. Geographic scope of stakeholder roles and variations in tourist types and preferences.

3.2 Conceptualisations of stakeholder involvement and motivation

Another key perspective on the stakeholders potentially involved, in particular the local ones, is the degree to which they are interested in and can be motivated to involve themselves in the development of local tourism. In a field study of local tourism in West Australia, [Alonso & Nyanjom \(2017\)](#) suggest four deliberately simplistic but illustrative archetypes into which local stakeholders can be grouped. While by no means exhaustive or universally valid, these archetypes may prove useful catalysts for further reflection that might reveal the need for more thorough investigation as INCULTUM progresses.

The four archetypes are summarized in Figure 4.

Based on: [Alonso & Nyanjom, 2017](#).

Figure 4. Four archetypes of local stakeholders.

1. **Tourism Advocates** constitute a highly diverse group in terms of the roles and functions they might otherwise have who are united by an enthusiastic approach to developing local tourism and readiness to promote it.
1. **Brand Developers** are the “thinkers” of the territory who actively develop and implement new ideas and are eager to present and promote them.
2. **Reluctant Followers** are cautiously optimistic about the possible advantages of increasing and developing tourism on the territory, but apprehensive about the possible negative effects.
3. **Conservative Residents** voice their concerns loudly and/or prioritize other objectives that are more important to them, even if some of them still recognize the possible benefits of tourism.

As also indicated in the figure, taking the original analysis a step further, the identified candidates for the respective stakeholder profiles may require different approaches when it comes to further substantiating their potential as assets or threats in reaching the goals set. Ultimately, such analyses can provide essential leads for assessing, for instance, how Tourism Advocates may be assisted in exerting an even stronger impact, how the Brand Builders can be further supported in their pioneering work, how the Reluctant Followers may be further empowered by becoming aware of new ways of contributing that offer them tangible personal benefits, and how the concerns of the Conservative Residents can be met in a constructive fashion and possible threats posed by them thereby reduced or avoided.

Here, we can take as an example Pilot 6, which is comprised of various local stakeholder groups who view the development of tourism differently. While none of them are outwardly against the development of the territory for touristic purposes, there are conservative residents who may begin to actively threaten the project if their interests are not addressed and respected. This project depends heavily on community approval, so the responsible partner of this pilot must give particular attention to this group in order to be successful. By responding appropriately to the views and needs of this group, they can encourage a more productive stance within these groups. Pilot 9, on the other hand, has been presented to have full community approval and is comprised of Tourism Advocates and Brand Developers. The responsible partner can therefore place their full attention on and energy into harnessing these groups’ potential, and perhaps encourage a larger workforce.

Being aware of the ‘status’ of local stakeholders and their dynamics, allows the ability to address them appropriately, creating more space to access untapped potential in boosting positive development.

3.3 Types of assets for and expectable gains from cultural tourism: an overview

In continuation of the above, the issue of whether and why the development of cultural tourism on the target territories is feasible on the one hand and advantageous to the people living there, on the other, deserves serious attention. Two basic questions need to be asked: “Why should tourists want to come here in the first place?” and “What would the advantages (and possible drawbacks) of that be?”. Only on that background can the individual stakeholders’ potential incentives and motivation to contribute be realistically assessed, as summarized in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Assets for and goals of attracting tourism.

3.4 Conceptions of cultural tourism

While the support of cultural tourism lies at the very core of the INCULTUM project, the specific sorts of tourism that the respective pilots envisage as having a potential on their territory (or territories) differ in essential respects. Moreover, the UNWTO definition quoted in Section 2 calls for further interpretation in several respects.

Based on the interviews conducted with key representatives of each of the 10 Pilots and other sources of information available at the present stage, a tentative list of the types of tourism targeted would need to include, inter alia:

- Architectonic tourism: (most pilots)
- Historic tourism: (most pilots)
- Religious tourism (⇒ Catholic tourism (Italy/Garfagnana), Islamic tourism (Italy/Sicily))
- Technology-oriented tourism (mines (Slovakia), irrigation systems (Spain, Portugal))
- Ethnic tourism (e.g., the Vlach population in Greece and Albania, ancestry tourism to Ireland)
- Educational tourism (e.g., France, Ireland, Italy/Sicily)
- Dark tourism (e.g., Ireland).

In addition, there are certain types of tourism where the cultural dimension, at least if taken in a narrow sense, is supplemented, or replaced by other Interests, e.g.

- Nature tourism, ecotourism (most pilots)
- Health and wellness tourism (e.g., thermal baths in Sicily, Greece, and Albania)
- Adventure and sports tourism (e.g., canyoneering and hiking in Albania, Greece, etc.)
- Etc.

To illustrate the diverse ways of defining cultural tourism we can cite a few examples from the

interviews with Pilot leads. Cultural tourism has been defined by Vincent Guichard from Pilot 6, Bibracte, as “tourism that is interested in discovering what makes up the heritage of the community of inhabitants of a territory”. This formulation reflects the nature of and sentiment behind the plans and motivations expressed by the team in Bibracte EPCC to revitalise, (re)organise and develop the elements within the pilot which give value to its landscape, nature, cultural, historical, and archaeological heritage. By contrast to the Irish Pilot 9, cultural tourism can be defined as deeply rooted within national, community and family history and identity and thus heavily emphasises the community-building aspects. At the heart of this project is the goal to awaken curiosity about Irish cultural and historical heritage and to point local communities and the Irish diaspora towards their ancestral past.

Given that the purpose at the present stage of stakeholder analysis is predominantly descriptive (see 2.2), we aim to filter out and classify as many shades of interpretation of cultural tourism as can actually be found within and across the current pilots, rather than matching them against any normative benchmarks from the outset. Considering, also, that obvious synergies between the different types of tourism envisaged seem to be crystallising already, we recommend keeping a door open to the present inductive angle also in continued work, taking an organic view of the input thus gained and thereby potentially contributing to the continued evolution of the concept of cultural tourism at large.

4 Current stage of organisational development across Pilots

4.1 Relationship between Responsible Partner and target community or communities

An essential difference between the 10 Pilots in terms of organisational issues is the geographic location of the partners responsible for the INCULTUM effort relative to the specific territory or territories targeted by that effort.

In the case of the Spanish, Portuguese, Swedish, and Albanian pilots, and also the Italian pilot targeting Garfagnana, the responsible partners are thus universities located at some distance from the target territories. In the case of the Slovakian pilot, in turn, while also led by a university, the university campus is located within the target territory. By contrast, the French and the Greek pilots, and the Italian pilot targeting Monti di Trapani, are all led by collaborative units created on the spot. The Swedish and the Irish pilots are even more complex in that the geographic and/or organisational distance to some of their (separate) target territories, i.e., Torsö and Ballyhoura respectively, is smaller than to others, i.e., Roslagen and Gotland for Sweden, and Connemara for Ireland. The complexity lies not only in the distances but within the fact that these pilots are constituted by two or more pinpointed tourist destinations and therefore have more elements to consider. Moreover, while the Swedish pilot is led by a university, the Irish is led by a grass root local heritage project which is not restricted to the target territories in focus in INCULTUM.

All of these constellations definitely seem to offer a viable basis for fruitful development and innovation. However, they are also bound to encounter different sorts of opportunities and challenges along the way in terms of logistics, stakeholders' possession and sharing of detailed local knowledge and establishment of personal contacts. This will require different emphases when it comes to monitoring and supporting the work of each pilot as the work progresses.

4.2 Stages reached in stakeholder identification and involvement

The stages reached by the individual Pilots as regards the identification and involvement of key stakeholders, also beyond the immediate INCULTUM project consortium, likewise differ substantially. While, for instance, the Irish, the French, the Italian (Garfagnana), and the Slovakian pilots have a relatively solid basis to build upon in terms of earlier work and alliances on tourism development, the work on the selected target territories in Greece and Albania, or on the Swedish island of Torsö, for instance, will be of a more pioneering character (while certainly not starting from scratch). This, once again, affects, the types and amounts of monitoring and support that are likely to be required during the process. The same applies to the degree of specificity of the information that we have found for the present first version of the Stakeholder Map.

4.3 Status on establishment of cross-Pilot collaborations and cross-fertilisations

Apart from the alliance already established, it is integral to the INCULTUM rationale that the 10 pilots should mutually share knowledge and experiences as the work progresses, thereby cross-fertilising each other, while also reaching out to other projects and networks supporting innovative cultural tourism in marginal territories across Europe. Examples of potentially relevant dialogue partners in the latter respect might be, say, the Slovakian [Barbora Road](#) and the [European Fugger Road](#) supporting historic and cultural tourism in mining areas in Central Europe (for the Slovakian pilot) or [Destination Bornholm](#) supporting innovative tourism on the Danish island by that name (for the Swedish pilot). Moreover, for two clusters within INCULTUM itself such links and cross-fertilisations have been anticipated and planned from the outset, namely between the

pilots in Spain, Portugal, and Italy/Sicily on the one hand, and in Greece and Albania on the other. However, given that such further developments are still in a preparatory stage, they cannot be subject to further analysis and evaluation in terms of stakeholder dynamics in the present version of the Stakeholder Map.

4.4 Schematic overview

Pilot	Geographic location of responsible partner	Local stakeholder involvement	Expected key drivers of the innovation <i>in situ</i>	Cross-Pilot links (where applicable)
Spain	External: University of Granada	Under establishment	Local Irrigator communities	With Portugal and Italy (Sicily) Status: To be established
Portugal	External: University of Algarve	Under establishment	Horticultural communities; associations of small organic producers	With Spain and Italy (Sicily) Status: To be established
Slovakia	Internal: Matej Bel University	Some present, extension is needed	Regional stakeholders in tourism; local communities; students and pupils	None
Italy Sicily	Internal: G.A.L. Elimos	Substantial, but extension is needed	Local rural communities; local associations interested in rural sustainable heritage.	With Spain and Portugal Status: To be established
Italy Garfagnana	External: University of Pisa	Some present, extension is needed	Local community; members; staff of the tourist-cultural sector; operators of nature-based tourism; pupils; young students	None
France	Internal: Bibracte E.P.C.C.	Substantial, but extension is needed	Local village communities; local elected authorities; professional organisations in agriculture, forestry, tourism, sports, and leisure	None
Greece	Internal: The High Mountains Cooperative	Under establishment	Local cultural clubs and societies; brotherhoods of emigrants; Vlach Community, local professionals and professional organisations (builders, farmers, young scientists)	With Albania Status: To be established
Albania	External: CeRPHAAL (Tirana)	Under establishment	Vlach community; other local communities; women (in the case of industrial heritage); the young generation; school pupils	With Greece Status: To be established
Ireland	External (for the special target areas Connemara and Ballyhoura) Internal (for Ireland,	Substantial	Local rural communities; mature men (in the recording of graves); More specifics TBD	None

	as a whole with the historic graves found there): Historic Graves			
Sweden	External: University of Uppsala	Under establishment	Local rural and peri-urban tourism-development organisation; stakeholders from local administration: village/town residents; DMOs	None

5 Individual Pilot profiles and current/envisaged stakeholder dynamics

5.1. Spain: Desert landscapes and oasis: Granada Altiplano

The Altiplano is an isolated and marginal area with unique landscape and historical irrigation systems. The municipalities that are participating are: Zújar, Castril, Castillejar, Jérez del Marquesado, Benamaurel, Baza and Lanteira. Tourism has been developed in the area since the declaration of Geopark by UNESCO two years ago.

The main empirical input for this first version of the stakeholder analysis have been qualitative interviews conducted between CBS research assistant, Caroline Agha Raad, and representatives of the Pilot: professor and coordinator Jose Maria Martin Civantos and researcher Elena Correa Jimenez, both from [Universidad de Granada](#). The team at the University of Granada has presented the project to stakeholders such as the seven municipalities (mayors, town councillors, culture, tourism, environment), the irrigation communities (presidents, secretaries, etc.) and cultural and trekking associations. They have worked and are working with many of them on other projects, and these stakeholders have responded positively toward this project. Brochures have been produced, to show the local population the objectives and methodology of the project. Perception surveys have been conducted for the local population, but results haven't yet been obtained. The objective is to obtain information about the local population's perception of the place as a tourist destination and their interest in the INCULTUM project. Results haven't been obtained yet.

[Data](#) regarding the present tourism (2020) in Granada is collected by the [Patronato Provincial de Turismo](#) organisation, which is also one of the partners of the present pilot. Tourists arriving to the province of Granada where the pilot is located are mainly national tourists (94,1%) whereas the foreign demand is mainly from France, Germany, UK, and Italy. It's important to take into account how the pandemic has impacted the sector. The number of tourists has decreased significantly, and the number of national tourists has increased compared to the number of foreign tourists due to travelling restrictions. The average age is 42,9. Most of the tourists coming to the province of Granada travel with a partner (56,4%) and they mainly arrive in private cars (86,9%). The types of tourism that are the most representative in the area: eco-tourism/nature tourism (18,2%), urban tourism (23,6%) and cultural tourism (65,5%).

Assets potentially attracting new tourists are the historical irrigation systems, local food production and beautiful nature including landscapes such as semi-arid areas, deserts, oasis, and caves. The cultural trekking routes and digital maps covering these routes are another asset. Similar [maps](#) have already been created in collaboration with other projects such as [MEMOLA](#)³. These digital maps will be created in collaboration with the irrigation communities among other local agents with the use of GPS apps and designed with GIS software. It will hereafter be uploaded on the website and given in paper format to municipalities and to the local population. Other assets are the local food production.

One of the goals of attracting new tourists is keeping people from moving away by increasing local employment and residents' involvement in tourism management. Furthermore, the team at the University of Granada puts emphasis of the importance of teaching in traditional agriculture

³ MEMOLA focuses on the study of four MEditerranean MOountainous LAndscape in Europe: Sierra Nevada (Spain), Vjosa valley (Albania), Trapani Mountains and Colli Euganei (Italy). The project aims to analyse cultural landscapes taking as a central axis the diachronic study of the relationship between human populations and natural resources- in particular soil and water- that are essential to generate agrosystems.

and historical irrigation systems to create awareness of environmental values and improve the residents' perception of local tourist activity. Other goals are to increase the use of sustainable farming methods, increase cultivation of local species and increase sales of local goods and services. According to interviewees, improvement in infrastructure is not needed. This pilot faces the challenge of keeping tourism vital amongst an aging population, though it remains unclear how this is to be achieved. Flexibility in adapting to the seven different municipalities will be needed in order to implement the ideas and interventions. The interviewees express concerns regarding the creation of strategies for the local management of cultural routes.

5.2. Portugal: Agrarian coastal plain: Campina de Faro

Campina de Faro is in the heart of the region Algarve in Portugal. The territory of the pilot case is, on the one hand, peripheral to mass tourism, on the other hand it has a rich and diversified cultural heritage associated with traditional irrigation systems and historic farms. The landscape and water heritage of Campina de Faro shows signs of neglect and degradation. Nevertheless, this pilot is qualified as a cultural tourism destination due to its high historical and cultural value, unique in the context of the national territory.

The present pilot is coordinated by the University of Algarve by a multidisciplinary team of professors and researchers from the fields of Landscape, Heritage, Economics, Sociology and Territory Marketing. The main empirical input for this first version of stakeholder analysis is a qualitative interview conducted between CBS research assistant, Caroline Agha Raad, and representatives of the Pilot, Desidério Luis Sares Batista, professor and coordinator at [University of Algarve](#), and Miguel Reimão Costa, landscape architect and researcher at the same university.

The focus is at this stage directed towards partners such as the IN LOCO Association and the municipalities of the three cities with which the pilot is related: identifying and contacting the main local agents and conducting interviews and surveys with the local population. Contacts with residents will begin shortly as part of a perception survey that are expected to be completed in March 2022.

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The tourism in the region Algarve is mostly foreign demand (79%), and the tourists are mainly coming from UK, Germany, Ireland, Holland, Spain, and France. The national market is also of great importance to the region, representing approximately 21% of total overnight stays in 2016. Their main interests are sun & beach (42%), the practice of sport (9%) and water parks (6%).⁴

The cultural routes regarding hydraulic heritage and agriculture are the main assets in this pilot. Gastronomy such as the Mediterranean diet is also expected to attract cultural/food tourists and is promoted by the Competence Center for the Mediterranean Diet, the University of Algarve, and the municipality of Tavira. The area is rich in heritage such as roman ruins and historic centres of the cities of Faro, Olhão and Loulé. Events such as music, food and culture festivals take place in Campina de Faro such as the MED Festival in Loulé, Seafood Festival in Olhão and the

⁴ Source: O Perfil Do Turista Que Visita O Algarve (2016).

Countryside Fest in Estoi are also considered assets.

The main goal of attracting tourists to this area is to encourage cultural, slow, and creative tourism as a complement or an alternative to the massive sun and beach tourism in order to stimulate positive synergies with other tourist destinations in Algarve and thus create direct benefits for the local communities such as education, jobs and increases in family income. However, the infrastructure needs improvements to meet such touristic demand. Some are viable in the short or medium term, for example cycle paths and footpaths, or new bus routes. Other improvements will be practically and financially feasible in the medium-long term. For example, trams and trains connecting Campina de Faro with the airport. Its financing is included in the proposal for the distribution of community funds for the “Portugal 2030” program and its implementation and conclusion is scheduled for 2027.

According to the team, the pilot should be able to provide a comprehensive set of high quality and diversified cultural attractions. Creative tourism and slow tourism approaches should be adopted to increase competitiveness, reduce the negative impacts from seasonality and attract more tourists. Slow tourism is a reaction to mass tourism, and it includes several touristic activities at the destination such as walking, cycling, guided walks, gastronomy, handicrafts and festivals. Another aim of slow tourism is to encourage tourists to spend more time in each place. Creative tourism⁵ is characterized by travels directed toward an engaged and authentic experience, with participative learning in arts and heritage. In conclusion, this pilot might also need re-branding to attract a whole new segment and create the desired types of tourism.

5.3. Slovakia: Mining treasures of Central Slovakia

The Banská Bystrica Region is Slovakia’s largest region by area but with a relatively low population density for Central Europe of 69 inhabitants/km². It is a predominantly mountainous landscape with the two larger towns of Banská Bystrica (i.e., Copper Town) and Banská Štiavnica (i.e., Silver Town). Hundreds of years ago, this region flourished due to its mining activities. Much has changed since then, but the remains of the abandoned mining sites and the architecture of the towns and villages stemming from that period are still seen as the key assets of the region.

For the following stakeholder analysis/map, a qualitative, semi-structured interview was conducted on the 12th of November 2021 between Maximilian Block, Research Assistant at CBS, and Prof. Alexandra Bitusikova, Head of Matej Bel University Centre for International Projects, and Ing. Kamila Borsekova, Head of the Research and Innovation Centre at the Faculty of Economics of Matej Bel University. Additional qualitative and quantitative data, which could not have been extracted from the interview, was as best as possible taken from existing project documentation, findings made by other WPs, stakeholder homepages and online media.

The historic town and the technical monuments of Banská Štiavnica were named a World Heritage Site in 1993 based on its example as a European medieval mining centre. The town is already a popular tourist destination for Slovaks, a development triggered by the pandemic, which led to higher domestic tourism demand. In addition to the [UNESCO site Historic Town of Banská Štiavnica](#), the region offers plenty of other mining sites that the pilot aims to promote further. Another potential asset, hardly known by people outside the town of Banská Bystrica, is the Radvaň Fair. During the second week of September, more than 300 craftsmen sell their products on the local market. The fair is inscribed on the National Inventory of Intangible Cultural Heritage in Slovakia, but it clearly lacks promotion. Two more assets could create awareness of

⁵ UNESCO (2006).

the region, although they might not be considered as representative of cultural tourism (see chapter 3.4). The first is "Ministry", Slovakia's biggest and most modern night club. It is located in Banská Bystrica and could attract a younger clientele. The second is the possibilities that the region offers in terms of outdoor activities like hiking and biking, as well as the beautiful landscape offered by the lakes that evolved from the old mining sites.

The region's infrastructure offers public transportation, such as bus connections. The town of Banská Bystrica has its own railway station that connects it to the bigger cities of Slovakia. Other services include restaurants, bars, hotels, grocery stores and shops that sell local crafts or food.

In conclusion, some tourism initiatives are already in place in this pilot. The pilot researchers aim to improve the promotion of the region to international tourists. The main goal of the pilot is to increase the Internet presence of the Central Slovakian Region in both Slovakian and English. In practical terms, this means the creation of a bilingual webpage aimed at both domestic and international tourists, unifying and mapping all the important regional tourism attractions and services.

5.4. Italy: Sicilian inland: Monti di Trapani

The main empirical input for this first version of stakeholder analysis have been qualitative interviews conducted by Caroline Agha Raad, Research Assistant at CBS, with representatives of the Pilot: Giada Lupo from the Local Action Group [Gal Elimos](#).

Monti de Trapani is located in the province of Trapani in region of Sicily and the three municipalities included in the pilot are: Calatafimi-Segesta, Custonaci and Buseto Palizzolo. The cultural landscape in this area has remained almost intact allowing the fossilisation of certain elements dating from various historical periods. The persistence of traditional irrigation systems of Islamic origin is also of relevant touristic potential.

The present cultural tourism in the area is mainly gastronomic, based on the region's Mediterranean diet, and sports tourism including natural routes, cycle routes and kite surfing. In the area of Laguna Marsala kite surfing is a key element for attracting sports tourists. Through this project, the team wishes to change the perspective and perception of the destination in a more cultural direction, similarly to Olympia in Greece.

Monti Di Trapani is only about one-hour distance from the regional capital but is nonetheless in need of improvements in infrastructure. New air routes, street restorations, highways and transport connections between the small municipalities are needed. Construction of a railway from Palermo to Trapani began but was interrupted and is currently in limbo.

The key assets potentially attracting cultural tourists are the region's Islamic legacy, the agrarian and the archaeological heritage of the area. The present pilot has a very clear target: et the Islamic market. This tourism segment has high purchasing power, as the interviewees expressed it. The offer is not aimed at religious tourists but rather at a general public with a strong sense of identity and cultural value, with particular attention paid to an Islamic public. To attract the desired market, other potential elements such as halal certification has been considered. Furthermore, the pilot would like to create a strong health and balneal tourism profile with Turkey as an example, using water resources, for example their hot springs. The team has carried out perception surveys within local stakeholders such as municipalities and farmers communities. The response toward the project has been positive so far. Covid-19 has resulted in a desire for alternative sustainable incomes.

The team wishes to boost the value of the Islamic legacy through educational programs directed towards the local population. These programs are intended to improve professionalism in the sector, in order to attract foreign investors, to develop luxury and leisure-based tourism, thereby attracting the desired target demographic. However, the purpose is not only to attract tourists but also to retain local talent and motivate people to stay. The team at Gal Elimos finds it necessary to manage the project with a so called “umbrella management”. In other words, the Local Action Group coordinates the project but at the same time empowers local rural groups to become agents that complement their traditional knowledge with innovative elements and thereby attract visitors. They are collaborating with local stakeholders such as the culture association: [L’officina studi medieval](#). They also expressed an interest in a collaboration with national and international organisations such as [FAI \(Fondo Ambiente Italiano\)](#) and [Euro-Arab Foundation](#).

The pilot is challenged in dealing with a seventy-year-old law and its application regarding water resources. The municipalities in Sicily have met difficulties in figuring out how to use their water resources appropriately, which is necessary to meet the health tourism requirements in regard to balneal offers such as hot springs. Sicily is not responsible for legislation on the area regarding water sources which makes it difficult for local municipalities to progress on desired programs and developments such as hot tubs. The law needs to be renewed according to Giada Lupo, and it will be voted on by the Parliament. They hope to get through with it in the end of this year or the beginning of 2022. The pilot is also trying to attract foreign investments and therefore they are dealing with the problematics regarding the [Sharia Minibonds](#). A law firm and an Islamic finance advisory firm are working to adapt Italy’s “mini-bonds” legislation to provide sharia-compliant funding options as an alternative to bank loans.

In conclusion, this pilot needs a re-branding of its area to attract a whole new segment, and create cultural tourism based on the Islamic legacy. Identifying the profile of the present tourist visiting the area as well as the increase in visits that is considered needed, possible, and sustainable is also relevant. It remains unclear how such a re-branding of the area can be done and how they will be dealing with the challenges that the management of the project by the locals pose.

5.5. Italy: Tuscan-Emilian Apennines – Garfagnana

This pilot is mainly limited to the small village of San Pellegrino, consisting of only 38 residents, which is administrated by two municipalities and two provinces, splitting it between the regions of Tuscany and Emilia-Romagna. Located at an altitude of more than 1500m, this village has its main background as a pilgrimage site.

For the following stakeholder analysis, a qualitative, semi-structured interview was conducted on the 15th of November 2021 between Maximilian Block, Research Assistant at CBS, and Michela Natilli, a statistician from the University of Pisa and supervisor for the pilot, and Maria Grazia Deri, a Migration and Roots Tourism PHD researcher. Additional qualitative and quantitative data, which could not have been extracted from the interview, was as best as possible taken from the existing project documentation, findings made by other WPs, reports, stakeholder homepages and online media.

While the village, located along the pilgrimage route of Via Francigena, has a long history of pilgrims visiting the Sanctuary to see the remains of the saints, another key asset of San Pellegrino is the “Don Luigi Pellegrini” Museum of Ethnography of the rural life, named after the

20th century spiritual leader of the village. That place contains about 4000 artifacts, unifying the culture of the village with its surrounding landscape, and is regarded as the main concern of investigation for the pilot officials (Lemmi & Deri, 2020). The project leaders intend to organize activities within the museum directed at pupils to familiarise them with the cultural identity of the village in that peripheral region. Another asset is the remoteness of the village which makes it attractive for people seeking adventure and nature-based tourism activities, like hiking and biking.

The village itself does not offer the infrastructure that might be needed to encourage tourists stay overnight. It has one hotel and two restaurants, but no bar, supermarket, gas station, or other shopping facility. There is a bus connection to the town of Castelnuovo di Garfagnana, which operates a few times per day. Apart from that, tourists can either hike to San Pellegrino, or take the car along the only mountain pass that leads to the village.

The diversification of the local tourism industry is seen as the main goal to improve tourist flow through the village. Through initiatives inside the museum, the project aims to raise awareness for a younger generation of students, whereby the place itself should receive better promotion strategies. They also want to hold training session for local stakeholders to strengthen their awareness of touristic activities. Further evaluation is needed to identify which stakeholders they want to address –.

Throughout the interview, two challenges became clear. First, it remains unclear whether the local workforce suffices to play a key role in tourism because of the small number of residents the village has to offer. Second, it is challenging to measure the tourism flows in the village since it is only done for municipalities or provinces, and San Pellegrino sits on the border between two municipalities and two provinces, which makes it difficult to identify the target groups.

5.6. France: Bibracte Morvan, Ancient Paths into the Future

Data from Pilot 6 was gathered through official websites, documents, and a qualitative semi-structured interview which was conducted on the 10th of November 2021 between CBS Research Assistant, Sarah Mariane Qwarnström, archaeologist and General Director of Bibracte EPCC (responsible partner for pilot 6), Vincent Guichard, and Head of the Heritage and Tourism Mission within the Grand Site de France (GSF) framework, Flore Coppin.

The team at Bibracte EPCC, founded in 2007, ran a survey⁶ (2021) with local communities and authorities, tourists, and partners. They have thus accumulated statistics regarding how tourists are attracted to the territory, which elements attract them, who the tourists are, where they come from, key words associated with the area, where the tourists stay, duration of stay, touristic activities, satisfaction levels, perception of touristic activity, and how tourism affects locals and partners. This research gives valuable insight into the nature of and intension behind touristic visits and relationships between local groups and tourists. However, Vincent Guichard has expressed the need for another methodological strategy for deeper insight into the significance of their data. They therefore feel the need for benchmarking to gain more insight into tourist behaviour.

Bibracte is the site of an ancient Gallic fortified town from the 2nd century BC, located in Mont Beuvray, Morvan, in the region of Bourgogne. It is the subject of the Bibracte Museum, which is well covered by its [website](#) and an active use of various forms of social media, which the Bibracte

⁶ Bibracte, ses visiteurs & son territoire touristique, 2021.

EPCC team manages. Bibracte is also often the subject of documentaries about the Gauls, and of local newspapers and radio stations. But these do not reach far in capturing potential visitors' attention. The town is mostly visited by families (staying on average 1 week), school children on fieldtrips (8,000/year, staying 1 night), and visitors from Paris, Holland, and Belgium. There are boarding facilities, summer houses, and other forms of accommodations that can be rented, and are more popular than hotels, which are rather outdated.

Protected by the Ministry of Culture and the Ministry of the Environment as an archaeological and historical site, Bibracte has been awarded the title of Grand Site de France in 2008. The main appeal of the territory is, however, emphasised to be its landscape and nature. The area's rich agricultural heritage and nature are key elements, which the team in Bibracte EPCC wishes to (re)organise, revitalise, and develop with the approval of local communities and elected authorities, by engaging the local population and workforce, and harnessing their large range of skills, as well as developing more activities (e.g., biking, horse riding, educational activities). They hope to achieve this to attract more touristic activity spread throughout the year and to encourage permanent residence. An 80% fall in population since the early 20th century has caused a fall in vital workforces and the abandonment of some of the territory's hamlets, in turn causing degradation of agricultural landscape, forest, and tracks used for movement between the 12 villages which make up the territory, essential to the development of the pilot. In order to revitalise the tracks and organise their maintenance, Bibracte EPCC have begun collecting and compiling maps through GIS. They are communicating with a neighbouring organisation outside of their 12 villages who have shown to take interest in this particular project and their methodology. The Bibracte team hopes to open such dialogues with more rural communities who could be interested in duplicating this project within their territories.

Regarding the aforementioned depopulation, the pandemic has in fact proved helpful in attracting inhabitants, as people have shown to enjoy working from home, together with the popularisation of 'third places' (community spaces from which people can work remotely, created outside of both home and office) in France, and the tranquillity of the countryside. A notable group moving to the territory are artists, who, according to Vincent Guichard, now outnumber farmers. In a territory of which a major part of its identity rests in its agricultural activity and heritage, this is significant. This can be built upon to attract visitors, particularly from Paris, as the latter is a hub for culture and art.

In addition to the issues caused by the fall of inhabitants, there are important problems concerning extraction and consumption of water, outdated agricultural systems in cattle production, lack of services, little access to supply, inadequate and insufficient public transportation and infrastructure (notably within schooling and health systems), unproductive advertising methods (organised at regional level), seasonality, and conflicts of interest between various stakeholders (i.e. between centuries-old local families and new residents/ between locals and owners of the forest/ between locals and water agencies/ between Ministry of Culture and Ministry of the Environment/ between hunters and tourism actors). Vincent Guichard has also expressed concerns regarding funding for Bibracte in the future, as their team is growing, and this project will without a doubt span longer than INCULTUM's timeline. A solution to this problem has not yet been proposed. The most important and urgent problem that Bibracte Morvan faces is that population must grow to counteract the effects of abandonment and to improve the standards of the territory's systems, on which tourism also depends. A major challenge here is to improve these systems in a way that the various stakeholders will all be content with. In view of the multiple conflicts of interest between the parties, this can prove

difficult and must be handled with thorough reflection and care.

5.7. Greece: Aaos, the shared river

The Aaos (the Greek name for the Vjosa river) runs through the Aaos Valley, which is located on the border of Albania in the Western part of Greece. The region offers mostly unspoiled, mountainous landscape on which rest a scattering of villages, cultural heritage sites, and the town of Konitsa, which is comparable in size to the town of Përmet, Albania.

For the following stakeholder analysis/map, a qualitative, semi-structured interview was conducted on the 17th of November 2021 between Maximilian Block, Research Assistant at CBS, and Dr. Sotiris Tsoukarelis, founder and president of “The High Mountains” cooperative. Additional qualitative and quantitative data, which could not have been extracted from the interview, was as best as possible taken from the existing project documentation, findings made by other WPs, stakeholder homepages and online media.

Like the Albanian valley, the Aaos area offers plenty of cultural heritage sites, like bridges and ancient ruins that are unique in terms of their architecture. Even the villages are diverse in the matter of their traditional music for instance. In many of the villages, a few small museums are spread around the valley. They exhibit photographs and old relics from the past everyday life in the region. As with the Albanian pilot, the Vlach population could be used as another asset. Known as a nomadic, Latin-speaking group living in rural, scattered communities, they are supposed to play a role in future tourism activities in the region, just like the Sami people in Lapland. They could introduce tourists to their way of living, their architecture when it comes to building houses, and their culture and food. The landscape also provides lots of outdoor activities, like hiking, climbing and canyoneering, thanks to its surrounding mountains which are the highest in the country.

According to statements made during the interview, an improvement in infrastructure is needed, even though that is in fact not evidence-based and therefore needs further research. The expansion of roads and the unequal distribution of hotels was expressed as issues that might require improvement in the near future. Besides that, each village is equipped with a tavern, functioning as both a restaurant and a local store. There are some villages that are connected by bus. However, using public transportation is rather challenging.

The future collaboration with the Albanian pilot is one major goal of the project, primarily to exchange certain skills, approaches, and knowledges from the counterpart. They also intend to give workshops for sustainable tourism purposes to the local stakeholders, but they do not plan to do so before they have conducted social research to find out about their wants and needs. For now, their main focus is on the execution of a sufficient and comprehensive stakeholder map, because the pilot itself has not collected all the data needed in order to create it. Nevertheless, the pilot responsible, The High Mountains Cooperative has already implemented a promising [sample of a stakeholder map](#) on the project’s webpage. The Pilot is obviously taking the participatory approach of INCULTUM seriously, favouring a bottom-up approach to the contents of project. The challenge this pilot faces is the limited lifespan of INCULTUM, which demands a certain pace of development, where this pilot risks falling behind.

5.8. Albania: Vjosa, the shared river

One of Europe’s last wild rivers, the Vjosa, that gives its name to the valley it runs through, is located in Albania’s border region to Greece in the Southeast of the country. It is a peripheral,

practically unspoiled area with small villages along the river and one bigger town, Përmet.

For the following stakeholder analysis/map, a qualitative, semi-structured interview was conducted on the 12th of November 2021 between Maximilian Block, Research Assistant at CBS, and Eglantina Serjani, a member of the CeRPHAAL (Centre for the Research and Promotion of Historical-Archaeological Albanian Landscapes). Additional qualitative and quantitative data, which could not have been extracted from the interview, was as best as possible taken from the existing project documentation, findings made by other WPs, stakeholder homepages and online media.

The Vjosa Valley offers multiple cultural heritage sites such as ancient ruins and bridges. Many of them actually need restoration processes, and better promotion in order to become attractive to tourists. The people that live in the region, the Vlach population, could be used as another asset. Known as a nomadic, Latin-speaking group living in rural, scattered communities, they are intended to play a role in future tourism activities in the region, just like the Sami people in Lapland for example. They could introduce tourists to their way of living, their architecture when it comes to building houses and their culture and food. Additionally, there are natural benefits about the landscape. Close to the town of Përmet, their small thermal baths of Benje already attract tourists, but it was mentioned during the interview that the place does not have the capacity to satisfy demand. Since it is not really included in the project, but still seen as a major flagship for the region, it will be interesting to see if they find a solution for it. Other adventure-based activities, like canyoning, hiking and biking are popular activities for tourists and locals alike (see chapter 3.4). There are companies, such as Active Albania who offer canyoning tours, which provide these kinds of activities.

Tourism is a fairly new in Albania and have only been an active industry for 20 years. The hotels of the region are only found in the town of Përmet, whereas the surrounding area has guest houses that offer everyday-life experiences. Restaurants and local stores can be found in the town as well. Transportation is mainly dependent on private cars, whereas public buses (only) operate between the town and the capital Tirana up to five times a day.

The majority of the people arriving are domestic tourists, even though more and more international tourists show interest in the valley. The fact that Albania isn't an EU member state isn't regarded an obstacle as the entry requirements are quite moderate. Most of the tourists only spend some hours, or at most one day in the valley. It was not made clear whether the project aims to prolong the stay of the tourists.

The INCULTUM partners CeRPHAAL and the municipality of Përmet want to give workshops to the local stakeholders, including the Vlachs, to strengthen their awareness of tourism and to suggest new, alternative products within the tourism industry. More emphasis on the collaboration with the Greek pilot is needed because only little exchange between the two partners has taken place so far, despite their cross-border status. Hereby, one interesting observation emerged: While the Greek pilot was defined as a four-seasons destination, the Albanian pilot noted significantly less potential during the winter months for their side of the valley. How can this perception differ when it is one valley only crossed by a political border?

5.9. Ireland: Historic Graves

Through a qualitative semi-structured interview conducted on the 11th November, 2021, between CBS Research Assistant, Sarah Mariane Qwarnström and archaeologist John Tierney of [Eachtra Archaeological Projects](#), and extracted data from various forms of official documentation, the

team at CBS in charge of WP7 of the INCULTUM project have been able to gather information presented below to form the first draft of a stakeholder report.

Ireland has a rich history, culture, and identity, to which the Irish and people of Irish descent have strong attachment. Traditions and stories maintained and told throughout generations are what Eachtra focuses on with the [Historic Graves project](#) since 2010. This project aims to excavate, identify, and map historic graves through GIS technology, and to publish the information onto their website to connect Irish descendants and diaspora with their ancestors through visits to gravesites and storytelling. Over 800 graveyards have been registered, with over 200,000 names dating back 500 years. With INCULTUM, Historic Graves has gone from being defined principally as a genealogical tourism project, to a [dark tourism](#) project as well, with a focus on history from the early to mid-19th century and the Great Famine in Ireland. Their plan is two-fold: The first, to stimulate community engagement and train the latter to register graves, and to take and post online video recordings taken with cell phones of community members telling family and community stories about the graves' histories. The most active groups in the mapping of graves are men over the age of 60. The second half of the project (not included in INCULTUM) is the development of tourist trails, connecting gravesites with other touristic activities linked with their beautiful landscapes, high-quality food, localised production, pub, and music culture.

The website has been highly successful in connecting diaspora with the burial grounds of their ancestors ([see here](#)). Counties Limerick (focus on Ballyhoura) and Mayo (focus on Connemara) are the focus areas (of which there are likely to be more) to develop tourism and hold massive potential for the development of touristic activity. Rural Ireland has a lot of geographical space with [low population](#) density, as well as enthusiastic and hard-working local rural communities, eager to work with Eachtra. They welcome tourism as a way to boost the economy and to share their stories, history and culture. They thereby have the appropriate basis for the creation of sustainable touristic activity, and cultural heritage developments to educate locals and tourists.

Permission, support and funding have come from various people, institutions and organisations throughout the years, notably Ballyhoura Development Lmt., Mayo County Council, the [Heritage Council](#) (An Chomhairle Oidhreachta), the [National Monuments Service](#), local communities (who initiate collaboration with Eachtra 50% of the time). Other unnamed development organisations and councils have been involved sporadically throughout the years but have contributed enthusiastically. However, communication with the National Tourism Development Authority, [Failte Ireland](#), has not proved fruitful. The interviewee expressed an inability to communicate and a wish for better understanding between the parties.

Public transportation is an issue, as a car is needed to reach destinations. Other aspects of infrastructure are also undeveloped, and the area described as 'wild' or 'bogland'. On the other hand, it has been expressed that there is good coverage in the way of accommodation and supply. Additionally, Historic Graves has had some coverage from national media and international media (CSN and BBC). The Eachtra team also have profiles on several social media platforms., These, however, show little activity and could perhaps be developed further to gain attention and to allow Historic Graves followers to maintain a day-to-day connection to the project.

5.10. Sweden: Escape into the Archipelago Landscape

Data was gathered through a qualitative, semi-structured interview between CBS Research assistant Sarah Mariane Qwarnström and Associate professor, Dr. Sabine Gebert Persson from

Uppsala University (UU), responsible partner for Pilot 10, conducted on the 12th of November 2021. Data has also been gathered through official websites and documentation. It is important to mention that this pilot is in the preliminary stages and has not yet reached far enough to collect information for a developed and comprehensive stakeholder map.

This pilot covers three rural locations in the South-East of Sweden: Gotland, an international destination and island in the Baltic Sea; Roslagen, a nationally known destination in the coastal area Northeast of Stockholm; and Torsö, a local-regional destination in lake Vänern. Despite their different profiles, the three locations have been said to have a rich heritage in farming, forestry, mining/foundry, sailing or fishing. All have a problem in common: how to attract tourists in a socially and economically beneficial and sustainable manner. It would seem that the above-mentioned elements can be built upon and exploited to create appeal for cultural tourism. The principal motivations behind attracting more tourists are job creation and attracting permanent residents, due to falling numbers of inhabitants and suffering economies. UU's intention behind studying these locations is to develop a better understanding of tourist behaviour in different contexts, to better organise touristic activity, in turn leading to financial sustainability. The partners at UU show an approach which sets them apart from the other pilots. Their strategy is to use a bottom-up approach where they, through meetings with stakeholders, identify the latter's needs. These needs have formed the bases for the data collection on tourist behaviour. The data and results will be shared through workshops with stakeholders, where stakeholders will, together with the researchers, discuss the implications of the data. These workshops in turn form the bases on which new activities and innovations can be formed. During the summer of 2021, the analyses preceded communications with some of the stakeholders due to the limited time from project start to vacation period in Sweden.

To gain insight into tourist behaviour, and for further communication with stakeholders, UU has run initial studies on tourists, local communities and DMOs through interviews, surveys, a GPS-logger (in Torsö) as well as mapping of changes in cell phone activity during vacation periods in the regions. This will be followed by more studies and analyses along with workshops where findings are presented. The goal of their studies is to work out what a contribution may be on their part to developing tourism in a sustainable and inclusive manner, structured on a bottom-up framework. Additionally, the team is communicating with local workforces within the destinations, such as restaurants, hotels, and bus operators. Information retrieved during summer 2021 is being processed and aggregated, whereafter the results will be shared in workshops. Statistics in behavioural changes since 2020 along with other preliminary information on the collection of data can be found on the [INCULTUM website](#). Gotland, despite receiving many visitors, has a 76% GDP/capita compared to the rest of Sweden. Tourists often come for the UNESCO heritage site of Visby and leave quickly. A clash lies here: this manner of visitation does not allow for meaningful economic growth, job creation or touristic development on the island. To get tourists to see more of Gotland, DMOs have structured their tours around the island in a manner where only a short time slot is reserved for visiting the heritage site. Tourists were evidently less satisfied with this, as this site is the primary element attracting tourists. Thanks to the data gathered from tourists and DMOs in Gotland, DMOs can now construct a solution to satisfy tourists and DMOs alike.

There are three main attractions in Roslagen: Öregrund, Gräsö and Östhammar. Each with their own distinct characteristics and challenges: All three suffer from seasonality and short length of stay (average 1 day), but whereas Öregrund and Gräsö may encounter times of overcrowdedness, Östhammar still struggles to find out how to attract tourists. UU has an open line

of communication with the DMO Visit Roslagen, which will surely prove to provide valuable insight. Through [Visit Roslagen's website](#), we know that Roslagen offers various experiences, culture, exploration, nature, relaxation, sports, outdoor activities, and history to tourists.

Torsö is additionally affected by seasonality and a drop in population. Their aim is thus to attract more tourism, and to find a strategy to have touristic activity spread throughout the year, in order to boost their local economy and number of inhabitants. They also offer the outdoors, experiences, sites, sports, and relaxation ([Torsö official website](#)). Their cultural heritage can perhaps be developed upon further to achieve their goal.

6 Difficulties and Challenges

During the preparation of this deliverable, a series of challenges have appeared that must remain in focus and – when possible – be analysed in depth.

6.1 Soft, undefined, or too long-term goals

Due to the very nature of INCULTUM, many of the goals of the pilot's regard development of the local community in various ways. It is therefore only natural to state objectives related to the attitudes of the local population such as to "create awareness of environmental values" or to "improve the local residents' perception of tourist activity" etc. Data on many of these issues is lacking both regarding the present situation as well as the desired outcome, the goal, and therefore it becomes difficult to measure whether the pilot is progressing as it should be. For some of these issues the present situation could perhaps be described more in detail as well as the desired goal, for the pilot leaders to be able to measure the outcome of their actions. For other aspects the goals may simply be too difficult to actually measure. This, however, shouldn't make the pilot abandon them altogether. Nevertheless, it would help to focus the action if these indicators or the lack thereof was stated as clearly as possible.

Another common characteristic is to want to counter the tendency towards depopulation, which is mentioned in many of the pilots. Here statistics may be found in most cases. The problem, however, is that the desired outcome most likely will have to be evaluated over a longer time timespan than that of INCULTUM. This does not mean that the overall goal should not be abandoned, but it should be stated clearly that its achievement lies beyond the reach of INCULTUM. A possible solution might be to define short-term goals, which will work towards the overall goal, and which can be achieved within INCULTUM and where the achievement can be measured.

6.2 Non-alignment of levels of development

The ten pilots are constituted by more than 15 mostly large geographical areas scattered throughout marginal areas of Europe. On top of that, however, the pilots find themselves at very different stages of development in terms of what the core activity is in each of them. In some of the pilots, this activity is still in the making at the time of writing this report. certain stakeholders are only now getting onboard. In others, the core activity is already up and running but is outdated in one way or another. The participation in INCULTUM of these pilots centers on updating the activity or adding new activities, and thus their starting point within the project is completely different.

This fact – that the lines of evolution of the pilots are not parallel – comes as no surprise. Nevertheless, it constitutes a challenge to the extent that a comprehensive analysis of stakeholders simply will have to wait for the pilots initiated by INCULTUM. Stakeholder mapping and analysis is not meaningful when the stakeholders are still to be completely defined and involved. But since the stakeholder mapping exercise is fundamental to the later analysis related to impact and exploitation, this imbalance will have to be dealt with.

6.3 Structural challenges

Part of these problems are also related to the differences between the pilot leaders, which in some cases are university-based groups of scholars, while others are constituted by NGOs or NGO-like structures that experience difficulties when it comes to resources and being able to make decisions and act swiftly. These elements are necessary in reach a certain level of managerial efficiency, however, to best take advantage of the limited time span of INCULTUM.

Project management and responsible WP leaders need to be aware of these difficulties that certain pilots might experience. It is in INCULTUM's interest to help advance the pace of development in the pilots that experience these difficulties and do what is possible to alleviate

these 'structural' challenges. Development does not have to run along completely parallel lines, but if cross-fertilisation is to be meaningful across all INCULTUM pilots, a certain alignment is necessary.

6.4 Cross-border collaboration

Another challenge is related to the collaboration between the cross-border pilots which is constituted by two groups of pilots: on the one hand, the Greek, and the Albanian pilots and, on the other, the Sicilian, the Spanish, and the Portuguese pilots. The cross-border collaboration rests on two fundamental ideas: shared cultural features and – in the case of the Greek and Albanian Pilots – geographical proximity.

As these five pilots are exactly the sub-group of pilots experiencing the above-mentioned structural and developmental challenges to a larger or lesser extent, the planned collaboration between these two groups of pilots and the resulting cross-fertilisation is still mostly non-existent. At this early stage, it is only natural, but INCULTUM management needs to monitor this particular aspect of the overall collaboration and facilitate it whenever possible to make sure that the challenges do not overlap too much.

7 Conclusions and next steps

In conclusion, each of the 10 Pilots created in the context of or integrated into the INCULTUM project displays a wide variety of opportunities for and potential benefits of promoting and/or expanding cultural tourism on the selected target territories. At the same time, the stages reached in the explicit articulation of the planned endeavours - including the identification and involvement of key stakeholders and formulation of measurable KPIs involving particular constellations - varies substantially. A major challenge now is to encourage and support a swift acceleration of the concrete considerations made on and concrete steps taken towards accommodating these issues.

On the basis of the above, a number of questions need further consideration in each Pilot which will be formulated in further detail and addressed in the course of the continued work of and collaboration between the Pilots, the WPs and the overall management of the INCULTUM project. As a first illustration of such questions that will require further consideration by individual pilots, the following may be mentioned:

- Pilot 3: How can the town of Banská Štiavnica avoid suffering from touristification soon?
- Pilot 5: Does the local workforce suffice to cater sufficiently for tourism needs? How can the officials align both pilgrims and pupils?
- Pilot 6: How can Bibracte EPCC and partners improve the necessary system of pathways and develop the area, while successfully mediating between the parties who have conflicts of interest concerning these issues?
- Pilot 7: Can the local infrastructure accommodate the mobility needs posed by extensive tourism, in view of substantial transportation distances? Who will provide the investments needed for improvements?
- Pilots 7 and 8: Why does the Albanian Pilot see itself as a primarily summer destination whereas the Greek Pilot calls the region a four-season destination? How can they avoid that younger people move away from the region?
- Pilot 9: How can Eachtra gather and organise the workforce needed to develop the tourists' trails (2nd part of Historical Graves project)?
- Pilot 10: How can UU ensure the development of sustainable cultural tourism in the pilot's three destinations while acting entirely externally to the destinations (i.e., not being part of any decision-making within the destinations based on the collected data)?

Identifying the challenges mentioned in Chapter 6 is the first step in finding solutions and elements that facilitate the collaboration between partners and pilots and thereby also the proper functioning and development of INCULTUM. Project management and the teams behind the analytical WPs – especially WP3, WP4, WP6 and WP7 – will monitor the development of these challenges closely gathering data, analysing, and facilitating the advancement of the specific pilots that experience the difficulties mentioned in Chapter 6. The cross-pilot collaboration and cross-fertilisation most likely will need facilitation from stakeholders external to the pilots in question. In the next report D7.2 Midterm impact, evaluation and exploitation plan due in month 18, these challenges will be revisited analysing the pilot developments more in depth to establish whether the monitoring and action undertaken to facilitate the pilots especially exposed to these challenges has worked as intended.